

THE FORCES THAT AFFECT TO THE BALL VALVE CONSTRUCTION

Huseynova T.

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, teacher at Industrial Machines (English) department

ABSTRACT

Dynamic mesh technology was used to replicate the erratic flow and flow force in the hydraulic ball valve with the moving ball. The hydraulic valve's deposited ball was seen as a moving object. The related flow field's boundary shifted as the ball traveled. It was possible to obtain the pressure distribution at various moments. Next, while the ball was in motion, the hydraulic ball valve's flow force was examined. The theoretical results and the numerical results for the static fluid force are essentially in agreement. The hydraulic ball's design and optimization benefit from the analysis's findings.

The ball valve is a ball valve with a ball-shaped closure. The seat corresponding to the ball is circular so that the stress on the seat is uniform along the circumference. Most ball valves also have soft seats that easily conform to polished surfaces. So from a sealing standpoint, the ball valve concept is excellent. The valves shown in Figure 3-60 to Figure 3-66 are typical of the ball valves available. The flow control characteristics obtained from a circular orifice moving through a circular seat and the dual pressure drop across the two seats are very good. However, if the valve is left partially open for an extended period of time under conditions of high pressure falling across the ball, the soft seat will tend to flow around the edge of the ball bore and eventually lock the ball in position. Therefore, ball valves for manual operation are most suitable for stopping and starting flow as well as for moderate regulation. If the flow control is automatic, the ball will continuously move, thus preventing this error from occurring normally. Because the ball moves on the seat in a wiping motion, the ball valve handles liquids containing suspended solids. However, abrasive solid will damage the surface and sole of the ball. Long, tough fibers can also cause problems because the fibers tend to wrap around the package. To save on valve structure, most ball valves have a miniature bore with a venturi-shaped flow path about 3/4 of the nominal valve size. Therefore, the pressure drop across the bore ball valve Bore reduction is so small that the cost of a fully bore ball valve is often not justified. However, there are applications that require a full port ball valve, such as the , where the pipeline needs to be raised.

Keywords: ball valves, design of ball valves, turbulence, corrosion, cavitation, static pressure force, velocity.

Static pressure forces

The fluid pressure inside the valve affects the function of the parts that make up the valve. The pressure acting on a surface will push the surface until the pressure on the other side is offset by the same pressurized fluid, or the force is absorbed by the valve. The force created by the pressure on a surface is expressed in Newtons [N] and can be calculated as the pressure multiplied by the size of the area upon which the pressure acts.

The normal unit for pressure is bar. 1 bar is equivalent to 0.1 N/mm². When the pressure is expressed as

overpressure in relation to the outside atmosphere, a g is added so that it is written "barg".

If 1 barg (0.1 N/mm²) acts on a surface of 100 mm², this will produce a force of 10 N.

To easily get a feeling for the size of a force, it is not uncommon to compare with how many kilograms it can hold. 10 N can hold a mass of approximately 1 kg.

The pressure area for a 10" closed ball valve is usually 50,000 mm². With a differential pressure across the ball of 100 bar, this gives a force of 500,000 N.(pic 1)

Pic. 1 The basic illustration of the pressure acting on a surface

The area of a circular surface is calculated by the radius squared, multiplied by Pi (pi = 3.14).

$$A = R^2 \times \pi = R^2 \times 3.14 \quad (1)$$

This force must be absorbed by the valve. If one allows the sealing surfaces alone to absorb this force,

this will provide a good sealing force which makes it easy to get the valve sealed.

However, if the valve is moved with this force present, this same force causes significant friction that must be overcome in order to create movement.

Pic.2 The figure shows the pressure forces in a ball valve with floating ball.

Even if one is able to move the valve with such strong friction, this friction would also cause excessive wear on the seal surface.

Flow

The flow of gas or liquid is referred to as either turbulent or laminar.

Laminar flow is steady over time and cross-section. In a circular cross section, a laminar flow will have high velocity in the center, which then decreases towards the edges.

Pic.3 The laminar flow

Turbulent flow is characterized by the fluid constantly changing velocity and direction of flow across the cross section.

Turbulent flow typically occurs at high velocities, abrupt changes in flow direction and/or changes in

cross section, as a result of both geometry and increased velocity.

Pic.4 The turbulent flow

Laminar flow gives a lower pressure drop and erosion than turbulent flow. Turbulence can also break down corrosion prevention layers in low alloy or corrosion-resistant materials. With turbulence, a corrosion inhibitor has little or no effect.

The different types of valves handle flow in different ways. A regulating valve should provide a certain pressure drop, which is achieved by reduced cross-section and subsequent increase in velocity. This often causes turbulent flow. Because the pressure loss associated with turbulence is not constant, it can be difficult to achieve a smooth adjustment.

Pic. 5 The example of the turbulent flow inside of the valve

A butterfly valve used for regulation will usually produce high turbulence at a small opening. This type of valve is therefore used primarily as a control valve for applications, where the valve normally operates in

a fully open position. For shut-off valves, it is normally preferred to have the least possible loss of pressure in the open position. These are therefore largely designed to ensure laminar flow.

Pic. 6 The example of the turbulent flow in a butterfly valve

This also applies to valves with reduced throughput, where the geometric design is even, so that turbulence does not normally arise, even though the velocity is increased locally in the valve's smallest cross-section. If the valve is mounted immediately downstream

of equipment or elbows that generate turbulence, this can create conditions that alter the characteristics of the valve. For example, a wedge-gate valve will be able to operate satisfactorily with moderate velocities if the flow upstream is laminar.

Pic. 7 The inner configuration of the valve to affect to the flow

This is because the velocity is low at the outer edge, where the open design of the valve type can generate turbulence. However, if this valve is located immediately downstream of a control valve, the open design of the valve type can amplify the turbulence so that it causes adverse effects.

Dynamic pressure forces
In a pipe system with continuous flow, the pressure forces in the system are balanced. This means that the pressure acts with equal force on both ends of a straight section. The system is therefore stable and will not move (pic.8).

Pic. 8 The scheme of the stable pipe system

Quick opening and closing of valves can cause pressure pulses caused by positive or negative acceleration of the fluid. The pressure pulses may reflect, for example, when they encounter shut-off ends, T-pieces, phase changes in the fluid or large expansions in a

cross-section. If several of these reflections meet each other, they could reinforce each other and produce a pressure which is several times greater than the original system pressure. Such a pulse can move with sonic velocity. (pic.9)

Pic.9 The schematic view of the pressure pulse

Even though such a pulse may only act for milliseconds, it can cause major damage since it is an unbalanced force in the pipe system. (pic 10)

Systems in which such pulses are expected to occur are braced with pipe supports that absorb the forces. For example, in the flare system, where there are quick-

opening valves, the system will have strong pipe supports and a slope on the lines so that a slug of liquid does not form. For systems where such pressure pulses are not expected, the result can be fatal, because the pipe supports may be crushed and in worst cases, the pipe may fail.

To avoid such occurrences, therefore, it is important that valves with large pressure differences are not opened too quickly. Furthermore, valves with high flow velocity must not be closed too quickly. For valves

controlled by actuators, it is particularly important to ensure that valves that may have a large differential pressure are limited in their hydraulic influx, since opening speed with incorrect operation can be too fast.

Pic. 10 The damage of the pipe system because of the pressure pulse

Seal surfaces

Seal surfaces are usually divided into two categories: soft and hard. The function of soft seal surfaces is achieved primarily by a soft material such as a polymer or graphite being pressed against a metal surface. The softness means that it does not require as much force or evenness of the metal surface to achieve an acceptable seal.

The function of hard seal surfaces is achieved primarily by two surfaces with good fitting being pressed against each other. In addition to a good fit, a strong force is also required to create an acceptable seal. Hard seal surfaces can consist of two metal-to-metal surfaces or a hard polymer surface against a metallic surface.

In the context of valves, the concepts of static and dynamic seals are often used. Typical dynamic seals are

stem seals, whereas the static seals will often be valve housing seals, where there is no movement and the seal must remain tight.

Soft seal surfaces

Soft seal surfaces are primarily used as seals where there is some movement, therefore requiring that good sealing be maintained during movement. This may be a seal between a stem and housing, between seat and housing or between seat and the sealing body. Soft seals can be sealed as a result of a mechanical pre-tensioning which ensures sufficient sealing force, and/or by the gasket being pressurized by the process. A stuffing box typically with graphite is mechanically pre-tensioned by the pressure from the gland flange.

Pic.11 The pressure displeasure in the gland flange

Although the gland force acts parallel to the gap to be sealed, this force will produce pressure in the graphite so that a sealing force is created normally on the stem and valve housing. The size of this force in relation to the gland force depends on the consistency of the graphite. To maximize the sealing force, it would be optimal if the gasket was so soft that it was almost fluid. The sealing force would then be equal to the gland force, but with the disadvantage that it would be extruded out of the gap that it should seal. The graphite

typically used in stuffing boxes is relatively hard in order to avoid extrusion. Therefore, only a small part of the gland force provides effective sealing force. This will be further reduced over time because the graphite becomes harder as it ages. The hardness of the graphite also increases with the pressure to which it is exposed. This means that the more the gland flange is tightened, the less the force increase will result in increased sealing force.

Pic 12. The tightened position

Soft seals have limited strength, so that if the pressure area is too large, the material is unable to hold the pressure forces. The result then is often an extrusion of the gasket material into the gap it is intended to seal. In the worst case, this could result in a full blowout of the gasket. A typical O-ring can have a tensile strength of 10 N/mm² and a softness that makes it extremely easy to compress. This means that the gap it can seal without extrusion at high differential pressures is typically as low as 1/100 of the thickness of the O-ring (in the unpressurized state). Apart from the risk of extrusion, the O-ring is optimal because its softness provides a high sealing force, which is enhanced with increasing pressure difference. Correct geometric design of the O-ring groove is important for the functionality and longevity of the O-ring. It is equally important that the cross section of the O-ring does not fill the entire O-ring groove, but allows the O-ring to move. Normally, an O-ring should not fill more than approximately 85% of the available volume of the O-ring groove. If this is exceeded, the O-ring may be permanently deformed if, for example, it produces a vacuum.

Soft sealing materials generally have temperature limitations, both maximum and minimum. At low temperatures, the material may become too hard and rigid, so that satisfactory sealing cannot be achieved. At higher temperatures, they lose strength and become susceptible to extrusion. General degradation of the material is also increased by increased temperature. It is therefore common to operate valves with soft seals within the following temperature range (may vary in relation to the pressure):

A valve can be used outside the temperature range for soft seals if the design is such that the seal is not exposed to the fluid's temperature, or where care is taken that the seal is not exposed to differential pressure at the same time that it is at the same temperature as the fluid. Usually, valves that are exposed to very low temperatures will have an extended bonnet where the stuffing box has a larger distance to the fluid. Otherwise,

soft seals in seats may be exposed to a higher or lower temperature when the valve is only open.

Hard seal surfaces

Hard seal surfaces are used primarily on immobile surfaces or where sealing only needs to be maintained at a clearly defined point. This may be a seal between two flanges, or back seat sealing between the stem and housing or between the seat and the sealing body. The high sealing force required for a hard seal to be effective means that there are also higher levels of friction over the sealing surfaces caused by movement.

Metal-to-metal seals that are subject to motion while the sealing force is also at a maximum must therefore be coated with hard metal in order to avoid abrasion to the metal surface.

Metal-to-metal seals of the same material/alloy may also be subjected to cold welding due to the high sealing force. This problem is particularly relevant to rotating parts, such as a plug.

Coating with hard metal on one or both surfaces will also counteract this.

Fluid

A valve is affected by the fluid flowing through it. The fluid can cause erosion, corrosion and cavitation on the metal surfaces, degradation of soft seals, wear on seal surfaces and clogging of fittings with subsequent locking of motion.

Erosion

For valves with fluids containing particles, there will be a risk of erosion damage if these particles strike the metal surfaces with high velocity. Particles will normally have higher net-weight than the fluid they are in. Where a change of direction occurs, they will be concentrated at the periphery of the change. Erosion is not normally a problem for valves without changes of direction or with large pressure reduction, as long as the velocity in the system is moderate. For valves with pressure reduction, it is difficult to avoid local high velocities and turbulence.

Pic 13. The example of the high velocity inside of the valves

It is then important that the valve is used such that the area with the highest velocity is kept farthest away from critical areas of the valve. For a traditional seat valve, where the flow runs from the top side of the plug and down, there will be a concentrated flow on the lower side with a high velocity. This also coincides with a change of direction. This can result in a small area with concentrated erosion. The solution is to mount the valve in the opposite direction, so that the flow comes from the underside and provides a more distributed flow in the area with the highest velocity and large change of direction. This will not necessarily eliminate the erosion completely, but it will distribute it over a larger area, so it will take longer before a dangerous reduction of the valve material occurs.

Corrosion

The materials selected for the valve must have an acceptable corrosion resistance against the fluid the valve is exposed to. For seal surfaces, corrosion is totally unacceptable, though it may be acceptable to have some general corrosion in the housing over the lifetime of the valve. For valves selected made of precious metals because of a corrosive and wet fluid, it is particularly important that the smaller valve parts have at least as good resistance as the valve housing and obturator. There are many examples where bearing rings of 316 stainless qualities have lost function due to galvanic corrosion when they have been inside the duplex valves.

Cavitation

Liquids have a vapor pressure at all temperatures. If the pressure is lower than this pressure, the liquid turns to vapor (gas). For valves where there is a drop in pressure, this pressure drop will be slightly different inside the valve.

In some places, there can be a risk of reaching a level below the liquid's vapor pressure. This results in gas precipitating locally. If the surrounding system is not below the vapor pressure, the system will quickly equalize. This results in the gas returning to liquid form again. This happens quickly, and the large volume difference between gas and liquid means that this causes an implosion. Implosions near metal surfaces can cause metal pieces to be sucked out. Paradoxically, the damage to hard metal surfaces is just as large as for soft surfaces.

This physical mechanism is called cavitation. Similar problems typically occur in pumps and boat propellers.

Degradation of soft seals

Soft seals can be degraded by the fluid we have in our facilities. Usually, the additives used in a well stream to ensure hydrate-free transportation and optimal separation represent a challenge for some of the soft seals used. The temperature itself also affects the degradation process.

Chemical degradation of soft seals is a common problem in connection with the specification of such sealing elements. Seals in the fluorocarbon group (rubber) are often more susceptible to chemical degradation than seals made of polymer (plastic). Although there are many types of rubber compounds which are specially adapted to various chemicals that are present in the fluid, this is often a design challenge. It is particularly chemicals such as methanol that pose the greatest challenges.

Plastic materials, however, are normally very resistant to chemicals and therefore lip gaskets are often used to a greater extent than O-rings, where it is known that these chemicals will be present. Rubber sealing rings will normally also be more susceptible to mechanical damage in gas service. This is caused by gas that penetrates into the core of the O-ring and which is not released naturally during rapid decompressions. When the O-ring's ambient pressure drops rapidly, the confined pressure is released into the surrounding volume. If the O-ring's natural pores are unable to release the trapped pressure quickly enough, the O-ring will "explode" and thereby lose its functionality. This phenomenon is often referred to as "explosive gas decompression failure". Plastic gaskets are not prone to this damage mechanism and lip seals are therefore often preferred instead of O-rings in gas service.

Some soft seals have an extensive network of pores and micro-cracks. This can lead to the penetration of liquid, causing the sealing material to swell. Such swelling can result in increased friction, and therefore cause operational problems or increased wear.

Clogging

Cavities in valves can be filled up with both particles and deposits from the fluid. This can prevent

movement of floating seats or prevent a gate from closing.

Deposits may also form on the seal surfaces that prevent them from meeting.

Hydrates can assume various forms, such as a “sludge” in oil pipelines or more solid matter in gas systems. Hydrates occur in a hydrocarbon gas/water mixture. Hydrates form under relatively high pressure and low temperature (below 20-30 °C). For a fluid where there is a potential for hydrate precipitation, there will usually be a risk of this occurring on parts of the valve where there is a lower temperature than inside of the main flow. This can apply to a cavity on a gate valve, for example.

In oil and gas production, the well stream also carries a number of different salt compounds. These compounds can precipitate inside the valves, producing a relatively hard coating. On the seal surfaces, this can prevent the desired quality of seal being achieved. In the worst case, the hardest forms of precipitation can also result in scratching of softer seal surfaces. For fluid seats, this precipitation can prevent movement and, in the worst case, result in full wedging of the seat.

Threaded connections

Working with valves requires that the principles should be understood so that personnel are able to safely remove and install threaded plugs in a valve housing.

The minimum number of threads engaged should be in accordance with the suppliers recommendations and company procedures.

Tapered threads

Pic 14. Parallel threads

For parallel threads, the gap between the threads is too large to be filled up and provide a full pressure seal. For parallel threads, therefore, sealing must be obtained somewhere other than in the threaded surface. A gasket is normally used. Alternatively, the plug can have a tip that ends in a metal seat.

Unscrewing parallel threads will result in immediate leakage, but is nevertheless poorly suited as a means to bleed off pressure.

Therefore, plugs with parallel threads should not be unscrewed when they are pressurized.

Regardless, always ensure that no person is in front of a plug when it is unscrewed.

Threaded bleed-off plugs

There are many different designs of bleed-off valves that allow controlled release of pressure, while also allowing satisfactory sealing to be obtained again

For tapered threads, sealing must be achieved in the threads. However, there is a misunderstanding in the market that this is achieved by creating metal-to-metal contact between the threads.

There would have to be very large deformation to achieve a continuous metal contact around the entire cross-section so that it can create a satisfactory seal. Instead, there must be a sealant that fills the gap between the threads. This could be Teflon tape or a lock-tight fluid.

In addition to creating the seal itself, this will also provide lubrication during tightening so that friction is reduced, while the risk of cold welding between similar materials is reduced. Lock-tight fluids will also lock the plug so that the risk of unscrewing, due to vibration, for example, is reduced. Teflon tape is prohibited in many facilities because of the danger of unscrewing. Teflon tape and lock-tight fluid used must be specified for the correct temperature range. The lock-tight fluid specified for the facility must then be used in accordance with applicable procedures. This also applies to the cure time for the fluid. When removing plugs with tapered threads, it is difficult to control when the plug loses contact with the threads and can be shot out. The sealant will also be destroyed by unscrewing, so that it will not be possible to achieve sealing again if it is discovered that the valve seats, for example, are not tight. Therefore, plugs with tapered threads should not be unscrewed when they are pressurized. Regardless, always ensure that no person is in front of a plug when it is unscrewed.

at any time. All these plugs have an outer portion with parallel or tapered threads that are screwed into the valve. This section must always be static. Inside this there is a new element that is used to bleed off pressure. This can either be operated by a threaded arrangement directly, or it may require a special tool to be able to loosen a spring-loaded sealing body. Some bleed-off plugs must be opened by screwing to the right, while others must be turned to the left to open. It is extremely important to find the proper procedure for the plug in question and to follow it. Whatever the design, it must always be ensured that the bleed-off plug's outer part is locked in the valve with lock-tight fluid or a locking bolt. During bleed-off, it is important not to use excessive force without a counterbalance on the outer part of the plug.

Pic. 15 The example of the counter balance during the tightening operation

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